

Analysis of the current state of implementation of fitness clubs personnel policy

Oleksandr Aghyppo
Galina Putiatina

Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture, Kharkiv, Ukraine

The article analyzes the current state of implementation of the personnel policy of fitness clubs in Kharkov. The directions of reforming the system of recreational and motor activity are proposed.

Purpose: *to reveal the main provisions of the mechanism for the implementation of personnel policy in the system of recreational motor activity (for example, fitness clubs).*

Material & Methods: *method of analysis of scientific literature and documentary sources, analysis of advanced domestic experience, method of system analysis, method of sociological survey, methods of mathematical statistics. The survey was conducted in order to analyze the state and prospects of development of the system of health and recreational motor activity of the population at the regional level (in particular, aspects of the implementation of personnel policy by fitness clubs). 53 respondents took part in the survey, among them 10 were representatives of the management of the physical culture and sport bodies and the "Sport for All" system, 12 were scientific and pedagogical workers, 31 were representatives of fitness clubs in Kharkiv.*

Results: *evealed the mechanism for implementing personnel policy by fitness clubs, analyzed the state and prospects of this area of work in the field of fitness.*

Conclusion: *as a result of the study, the functions that are performed by a competent fitness club specialist are summarized. A mechanism for the implementation of personnel policy by the subjects of the fitness industry has been formed and the principles for its implementation have been substantiated. Established priority measures to reform the fitness industry in the context of the implementation of personnel policy.*

Keywords: *personnel policy, fitness club, subjects of the system of recreational motor activity, optimization.*

Introduction

In modern conditions, the issue of creating the necessary conditions for attracting people to the daily and specially organized motor activity of proper duration, intensity and regularity is being actualized. In Ukraine, for a number of objective and subjective reasons, significant reserves remain to be realized to increase people's motivation for physical activity, form relevant interests, use the organizational and management capabilities of various subjects of the recreational motor activity system, determine strategic directions and substantiate innovative technologies to create an environment, encourage the use of recreational and motor activity [1; 7; 9].

The organizations of the fitness industry, namely fitness clubs, and their main active resource, human resources, can make a significant contribution to improving the health of citizens and establishing a healthy lifestyle [3; 5; 6].

The targeting of effective management in the field of fitness should take the vector of optimal personnel policy in all subjects. Meanwhile, factors hindering the development of the fitness industry in our country, lacked personnel and low level of professional training of specialists working in this area [2; 4; 8]. This gives grounds to consider the personnel policy of the subjects of the system of recreational and recreational motor activity of the population (in particular, fitness clubs) as an independent subject of research.

Purpose of study: to reveal the main provisions of the

mechanism for the implementation of personnel policy in the system of recreational motor activity (for example, fitness clubs).

Material and Methods of the research

In order to analyze the state and prospects of development of the system of recreational and recreational motor activity of the population at the regional level (in particular, aspects of the implementation of personnel policy by fitness clubs), a survey was conducted. 53 respondents took part in the survey, among them 10 representatives of the management bodies of the physical culture and sport and the "Sport for All" system, 12 scientific and pedagogical workers, 31 representatives of fitness clubs in Kharkov.

Research methods: analysis of special scientific literature and documents, analysis of advanced domestic experience, method of system analysis, organizational analysis, sociological survey method, methods of mathematical statistics.

Results of the research

Personnel policy is a strategic activity with goal-setting, ideological and software formation of the development and use of human, labor, human resources as the main prerequisite for the construction of any economic unit. This activity is systemic and dynamic in nature and is implemented by state and local government bodies, directly by economic actors and other stakeholders. Personnel policy is carried out through

targeted joint actions of all stakeholders in the format of social dialogue.

In a broad sense, the term "state personnel policy in the field of fitness" should be understood as the systemic activity of state authorities aimed at the formation, improvement, implementation of a set of standards, professional requirements for employees, pedagogical and other industry workers, the criteria for their selection, training and retraining, raising the level of qualification, rational use of personnel potential and its preservation on the main quantitative and qualitative forecasts and development prospects of the fitness industry..

As the results of the organizational analysis of the activity of fitness clubs show, the personnel policy is closely connected with all branches of their economic policy. The generalization of the advanced domestic experience in the formation and implementation of personnel policy in the field of fitness has shown that in practice a mechanism is being implemented which is based on fitness clubs, focusing on organizational goals, analyzing the influence of internal and external factors, apply certain principles that determine the personnel policy of an individual subject (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Mechanism for the implementation of personnel policy by the subjects of the fitness industry

Personnel policy provides for the development of specific actions to manage the staff to address the objectives of the fitness club. Competently developed personnel policy allows you to structure all activities with staff into a coherent system, which in future will be aimed at increasing staff productivity and the performance of the club. As you know, the fitness club staff consists of:

- attendants;
- coaching staff;
- specialists of additional services;
- leadership.

In the area of work and staff training, administrative management should solve certain tasks, namely:

- recruitment of employees who will carry out activities within the framework of a fitness project (in accordance with official duties), taking into account the steadily growing demand for specialists in the fitness industry;
- carrying out training work among staff in the development of communication skills (the ability to work a fitness trainer in clubs of different formats and customer requests)
- providing opportunities for productive activities and at the same time reducing the staff turnover rate (building team spirit), taking into account the need to update and diversify services.

The analysis of this work of 15 fitness clubs in Kharkov allowed the following ways to search for personnel to be established:

- placing an ad on the search for instructor group programs on thematic platforms on the Internet and city boards, followed by an interview;
- self-education of future instructors by a specialized specialist in fitness.

And all clubs use both of these ways, because:

- the fitness club teaches future professionals precisely those aspects of work that satisfy the needs of visitors to a particular fitness club;
- an opportunity to learn more about a potential fitness trainer before actual employment (conducting trial workouts, individual examinations, psychological factor assessment);
- increases the level of loyalty and involvement in the activities of the club;
- tuition allows you to increase the income of the club.

Along with this, the disadvantage is that these instructors are not experienced, therefore, it is necessary to carefully monitor the quality of the services provided.

As a result of the study, we found that, according to the respondents, the competent fitness club specialist performs the following functions:

- 1) recreational and educational;
- 2) value and health;
- 3) motivational;
- 4) social and cultural;
- 5) educational.

(The degree of consistency of the respondents is $W - 0,74$)

It was also found that 77,3% of respondents consider the level of provision of domestic fitness clubs with qualified specialists in management, marketing and administration is not high enough. A significant number of specialists surveyed (66,9%) consider the level of provision of domestic fitness clubs with qualified fitness trainers is not high enough. This, in our opinion, is explained by the chosen ways of implementing the personnel policy of the administration of the studied fitness centers, which need to be optimized and coordinated with all the subjects of the system of recreational and physical activity of the population.

This fact is confirmed by the respondents' ranking of the

specified personnel selection criteria in the system of fitness clubs:

- 1) the level and profile of education;
- 2) professional skills;
- 3) the nature of the motivation to work;
- 4) personal skills;
- 5) level of motivation;
- 6) age;
- 7) appearance;
- 8) gender.

(The degree of consistency of the respondents is $W = 0,71$) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Criteria selection of staff in fitness clubs

It was also found that 87% of respondents are confident that having a higher education diploma cannot be fully considered the final point in the education of a specialist in the field of fitness. Fitness is not a field in which a person, when he has received a certificate or diploma, can work for many years in the same way. Fitness trainer must constantly improve, possess certain personal qualities. This process is creative and requires a search for new approaches.

A certain place in the implementation of the optimal personnel policy is given to the difficulties that exist in the work of a fitness specialist ($W = 0,81$).

- 1) Set and acquisition of groups.
- 2) Most busy social work.
- 3) Lack of educational materials.
- 4) Deficiencies in the medical support of the training process.
- 5) The difficulties associated with the conditions of life and life.

- 6) Insufficient personal experience of coaching.
- 7) Lack of a coordinated friendly team.
- 8) Insufficient development of some personal qualities and character traits.
- 9) Lack of skills to organize their work rationally.
- 10) Disadvantages of management and marketing of fitness services.
- 11) Large workload of economic issues.
- 12) The difficulties associated with underestimation of recreational and motor activity of the population, in particular, young people.

As shown by the results of the study, personnel policy is closely connected with all branches of the economic policy of the organization. From the main goal of the personnel policy, it is possible to derive sub-goals for personnel management, for example, to provide labor resources of a certain quality and quantity of a fixed term, for a fixed period, for certain jobs. On the basis of such targets, you can determine the content of personnel policy in the organization. The basic principle of personnel policy is that it is still necessary to achieve individual and organizational goals.

Conclusions / Discussion

Summarizing the advanced domestic experience in the formation and implementation of personnel policy in the field of fitness showed that in practice its basic provisions are already implemented in accordance with certain principles, based on the goals of fitness clubs and analyzing the influence of internal and external factors determining the personnel policy of the subject. Analysis of current aspects of the problem of implementation of personnel policy in the field of fitness, based on the results of the study, showed that the priority measures for its reform are: consolidating at the legislative level the issue of working in the fitness clubs of specialists exclusively with specialized physical education (81,7%); expansion of the network of available fitness clubs (64%); development of accessible tools for organizing self-healing and recreational motor activity of the population (58%). Issues of state regulation and control over the functioning and development of the fitness industry, in particular, the implementation of personnel policy by fitness clubs, and representatives of the private sector remain debatable.

Prospects for further research are to develop an optimal model of personnel management in the field of fitness.

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Information about the Authors

Oleksandr Aghyppo: Doctor of Science (Pedagogical), Professor; Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture: Klochkivska str. 99, Kharkiv, 61058, Ukraine.

ORCID.ORG/0000-0001-7489-7605

E-mail: aghyppo@yandex.ua

Galina Putiatina: PhD (Physical Education and Sport), Associate Professor; Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture: Klochkivska str. 99, Kharkiv, 61058, Ukraine.

ORCID.ORG/0000-0002-9932-8326

E-mail: putiatina.g@gmail.com